

Study of nanoscale effects on carbon filament growth during catalytic methane decomposition for high-purity hydrogen production

Master's Thesis

AUTHOR: Palomares Ferrando, Adrià

External cotutor: PRIETO GONZALEZ, GONZALO

Experimental director: ATASHI, NILOUFAR

ABSTRACT

Hydrogen is considered as one of the most promising substitutes for fossil fuels in various energy applications. However, hydrogen production commonly relies on hydrocarbon reforming at present, which entails substantial net carbon dioxide emissions. Therefore, significant efforts are being made to produce hydrogen with a zero-carbon footprint. While water electrolysis remains an ultimately preferred but comparatively costly route, catalytic methane decomposition (CMD) is being regarded as an approach to produce high-purity CO_x-free (so-called turquoise) hydrogen while “sequestering” carbon as a solid side product. Solid carbon nanomaterials are appealing for a wide range of markets. Moreover, the overall MD process may become net CO₂ negative if biogenic methane, e.g. in biogas, is applied as feed. The use of metal catalysts in CMD allows lower operating temperature, thereby reducing the cost of the equipment necessary to perform the process and enabling integration with hydrogen selective recovery through electrochemical pumping. Critical to optimize hydrogen production rates, adjust the characteristics of the carbon side-product and to enable long-term operation is to control the structure and growth mode of the carbon filaments on the catalytic metal nanocrystals. This thesis, investigates the behaviour of oxide-supported 3d metal nanocrystals in the CMD reaction. The impact of nanocrystal size and composition on the CMD reaction rates and the prevailing carbon filament growth mode are assessed on model catalysts using methods such as TEM, TGA and Raman spectroscopy. The results are significant for the optimization of CMD catalysts which operate under mild reaction temperatures (≤ 873 K) and wherein metal nanocrystal detachment from the oxide carrier is prevented, which are essential aspects towards the industrialization of quasicontinuous CMD processes for turquoise hydrogen production.

Keywords: Catalytic methane decomposition, metal nanocrystals, hydrogen economy, solid carbon nanomaterials, filament growth.